

Focus groups on metadata

Report for the proposed Research Data Shared Service on focus groups held between May and October 2016 and the metadata issues and requirements identified

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Thanks are due to the research support staff at all the institutions we visited for setting up these consultations; and of course to the researchers, technicians, research managers, publishers, funders, repository managers and support staff who wholeheartedly gave up their time to discuss frankly the difficulties, benefits and future requirements for creating, recording, submitting, sharing, storing, securing and searching their research data.

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Executive summary

Focus groups expressed concern about a number of areas with regard to metadata. Some can be addressed by training and support, many can be addressed by suppliers working with institutions and Research Data Shared Service. A few require new technologies or culture change.

Early creation and collection of metadata was often mentioned. This can be achieved through the use of dynamic data management plans so that metadata is collected from the planning stage and updated throughout the data collection and analysis process. Systems should preserve the form and content of the deposited data while allow updating of the metadata to link to related datasets, subsequent publications and other materials which may have been created after the data was deposited. They should also allow updating of keywords and descriptive materials to reflect changes in the discipline. The facility to allow metadata to include links to other Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and URLs (where a DOI does not exist) is essential.

It is often assumed that the collection of metadata will involve researchers in arduous and time consuming form-filling at data deposit time. This is undesirable and unlikely to produce good metadata. Instead, automation of tools, collection processes, equipment and metadata collection integrated into researchers' workflow throughout the research will, ideally, allow a push button submission of the data, with metadata already attached, to the repository.

Concerns were frequently expressed by users and creators of very large data and by users and creators of sensitive data which will have specific confidentiality and ethical considerations. The Research Data Shared Service will need to bear in mind these considerations if it is to provide a service to all academic researchers.

In order to fit with researchers' existing workflows, the Research Data Shared Service will need to provide some level of integration with local, national and international services. Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), DataCite and GitHub were frequently mentioned.

Introduction and methodology

This work was commissioned as part of Jisc's pilot Research Data Shared Service ([RDSS](#)). It was supervised by John Kaye and Dom Fripp. The focus groups were conducted jointly with Tom Parsons and Rob Johnson from Research Consulting who were looking at data and cultural issues while I concentrated on metadata issues.

The focus groups consisted of brief presentations, discussions, sometimes in small groups, and individual written feedback using various prompts. In some cases, if the institution preferred it, we conducted individual interviews covering the same ground as the focus groups. The outputs from this work were use cases which appear as an appendix to this document. The use cases were produced from all the participant activity in the focus group, some transcribed directly from hand written participant forms and some noted by us during the discussions and interviews. Nine focus groups were held and participants came from 11 of the 12 RDSS pilot institutions and from CREST, a consortium of 22 smaller and/or specialist institutions, which is also part of the pilot.

The themes emerging from the use cases are summarised below.

Automation and API

A key requirement is for metadata to be produced automatically wherever possible. Perhaps the most obvious example of this is the need for scientific equipment to have a sufficient API or to produce metadata which is already or can easily be attached to, or form part of, the data itself. But there are many other examples:

- a. The production of metadata as images are produced and stored;
- b. File structures and/or folders bequeathing metadata or a metadata template to any file created in the right place; “often the folder structure is part of the metadata, it shows what’s what”;
- c. Similarly, default licensing terms being suggested or attached as the metadata is created or submitted;
- d. Electronic lab notebooks publishing their metadata directly to a repository or intermediate store;
- e. At file creation/saving the software to suggest metadata or provide the researcher with dropdown lists relevant to the subject or discipline.

Other requirements in this area include:

1. Counting and tracking those who access my data/metadata;
2. Minting DOIs as part of the submission process (esp. for unpublished data for conferences etc.)
3. An API to the data served by the RDSS;
4. Interfaces to understand complex data e.g. browsable map interface for remote sensing data.

Authoritative assertions, ownership and policy matters

As the use of metadata grows and more services consume metadata, its provenance and authority becomes very important. Metadata will be more valuable if the consumer (whether human or machine) knows that it is authoritative. So the right authorities will need to make these assertions e.g. the university will assert that I am a member of staff, the funding body will assert that I did indeed receive XYZ grant, my collaborators may confirm the collaboration through similar assertions. ORCID is an example of a service which is moving towards adding value to its service through the use of such assertions.

A question frequently asked by research managers is “Who pays for metadata creation and sharing?” While that question can be answered by funder and institutional policies, the ownership of data and metadata is an issue which may need clarification. It is often not stated because there is a tacit agreement in the area to “carry on as normal” without challenging the assumption that researchers take “their” data with them when they move institution. Whether institutions want to claim the ownership which they probably could exercise is uncertain; since this would ask questions such as does the researcher have a lifelong right to access that data? and does the institution have a long lasting responsibility to store, preserve and manage access to that data?

Data management plans and procedures

Probably the most frequent point made during this work, from several different roles within research, was that metadata must be created early in and throughout the research process. By the time the researcher is considering publication or submission of data to the repository, much of the key

information which may underpin future analysis or reproduction of that data may have been lost, discarded or mislaid; the researchers may have moved institution and their focus may have moved to the next project. So a very important component is to allow data to realise its future value through reanalysis and reuse is dynamic data management plans which require metadata creation at the planning stage and also require updating of metadata throughout the process and allow updating after the data has been created and published. This metadata needs to be useful to machines and humans so would not just consist of key words and identifiers but also readme files/sections, free text descriptions etc.

Although the creation and recording of metadata should be required, its immediate public release may not be desirable for ethical, security or other reasons, including the fear of being “scooped”. If data is automatically released or required to be released immediately on creation, the metadata which allows others to make sense of that data may be withheld for a specified short period.

Equipment, instruments, machines

Procedures will need to be flexible enough to accept and integrate a mixture of auto-generated and manually entered metadata. Although RDSS is primarily concerned with preservation and long term storage, to researchers the distinction between storage for active and archived data can be restricting and artificial. Active data could be archived automatically in some circumstances. Liaison with vendors will be important in:

- a. Pushing forward automatic metadata collection and storage;
- b. Avoiding use of proprietary file formats for interoperability and future proofing;
- c. Encouraging generation of fullest metadata possible (e.g. for images, traceability and reproducibility);
- d. Using lab notebooks to integrate automatic data and manually entered data and allow “push button” submission to repositories;
- e. Creating virtual environments for security and ethical reasons, where data itself can be worked on without downloading and only non-confidential and anonymised analysis may be exported.

Guidance and training

The main role in producing and disseminating this will be for the institution, but Jisc will need to provide RDSS briefing materials and templates and coordinate best practice to avoid duplication. System and equipment vendors also have role to play and PIs and research managers will need to monitor dissemination to all team members to achieve consistency of practice. Guidance and help materials need to be built into the process, encouraging early consideration and creation of metadata from the data management planning stage through to submission and beyond. High quality documentation, guidance and training will only be achieved if all key players are collaborating: researchers, managers, system and equipment vendors, service providers, funders and research support staff.

Integrations and crosswalks

Researchers require interfaces which allow the use of discipline-familiar metadata terms at data entry and search points but at the same time allow dissemination and discovery outside of and between subject communities. Any metadata and submission requirements should fit with researchers’ workflow

and common practice as far as possible. So integration with local services and international ones, GitHub or arXiv, for example, should be a priority. There should be clarity around the role of existing services such as the UK Data Archive and local CRIS. Consideration should also be given to tools which allow management reporting across a variety of researcher-practice and metadata workflows. Respondents emphasise the important role of metadata templates in allowing researchers to “create once and use many times” across different funder and reporting requirements. Inter-institutional national and international collaborations are common place and increasing, so RDSS should enable such access and collaboration not be perceived as a barrier to it.

Links to other locations and datasets

To realise the potential of stored metadata and data, it must be possible to link to a variety of other sources, in particular:

- a. Links between datasets, where there are logical or content dependencies or where, for example, an experiment is running daily, it may be desirable to link to an annual result summary or the latest available run results, parallel experiments or controls;
- b. Linking the DOI of the dataset to that of journal articles and vice versa;
- c. Searchers may wish to use a “more by this researcher” button;
- d. Buttons to allow metadata to be used to search for “datasets from similar projects” or “has this experiment been reproduced?”;
- e. Metadata stored or accessed separately from the dataset can be revised/updated with links to subsequent publications, “more detailed” or “less detailed” buttons.

Metadata fields

Suggestions include:

- a. Unique IDs for people and organisations, ORCIDs to be used instead of biographies;
- b. Records of location of other data for related and/or collaborative projects;
- c. Properties that may impact preservations, e.g. software dependencies, file formats;
- d. Embargo dates, NISO access and licence indicators (cf. CrossRef);
- e. Multiple fields for projects giving rise to or dependent on this data;
- f. Project goals, free text descriptions of project, experiments, methodology etc.;
- g. Language of the data, language of the metadata;
- h. Where and when created;
- i. Version information and links to other versions (see above);
- j. Software and commands necessary to reproduce files;
- k. More metadata rather than less;
- l. Ownership clarified and all contributors credited not just the PI;
- m. A collaboration prefix/field so one institution does not get all the credit;
- n. Flexibility to include metadata on digital objects, APIs, data dependent on virtual environments etc. Don't depend on file format field which may not be adequate.

Quality

Clarity, detail and accurate search functions were frequently mentioned. The quality of metadata is viewed as important for a variety of reasons: aiding discovery, reporting to institutions and funders, finding collaborators, reproducibility, aiding reuse and reanalysis, understanding methodology, verification and refereeing, clarifying licensing, security and ethical conditions.

Reuse

Reuse is of great importance in getting value and progress from research data. Metadata should play a key role; issues mentioned included:

- a. Enables funders to assess the results of funding and funding programmes;
- b. The importance of consistency in coding metadata so that researchers can reliably work with others' data;
- c. The creators of the data should be able to trace all reuse and reanalysis;
- d. Templates can be created from previous datasets to allow rapid creation of metadata;
- e. Metadata collected from DMPs and instruments and equipment can be attached to new datasets to render manual entry of metadata unnecessary;
- f. A portable, personal metadata "profile" which can travel with an individual researcher and be applied as a template (perhaps multiple profiles for different areas of their work?), not only would this save time but aid consistency and comparability between datasets.

Search

Researchers want easy search and discovery for their own and other people's data. In particular:

- a. Searching via and integrated with DataCite;
- b. Some want to agree disciplinary vocabularies and keywords, others want to provide and search free text, both should be catered for;
- c. Search function must allow searching of multiple fields. Discipline specific mime types should be investigated;
- d. Where datasets or collections are large (e.g. genomics) data mining techniques should be available;
- e. Metadata and keywords should be updatable to reflect changes in vocabularies and practice;

Security, permissions and ethics

Any service will need to capture the types of sensitive data which are stored. Institutional policies will need to be in place and actively applied to approve the storage of different types of sensitive data. Tools like DMP online will be helpful in this regard. Metadata should include who should have access, what the access conditions are, how permission may be obtained and what licences if any have been applied. Permissions given by original subjects should be recorded. Where only parts of the data have confidentiality issues, this should be made clear and it should be possible to download unaffected data. The submission process should facilitate this distinction being applied by the depositor. Ethical approvals should be recorded and updated where necessary. Industry partners would need to be confident that confidentiality, security and IP issues have been addressed.

Updates

The metadata associated with datasets should be updated to link to publications, preferably with DOIs. Several respondents mentioned the possibility of CrossRef and DataCite automating this process so that as a publication is made or a DOI minted, the DataCite metadata for the dataset is automatically updated; and RDSS and /or local repositories should pick up these updates. As mentioned above, authorities should be able to assert certain metadata such as funding details and institutional affiliation but it would also be desirable to allow others to add metadata to enrich the data (it will be necessary to differentiate depositor supplied metadata, authoritative assertions and crowd additions / suggestions / comments). Certain aspects of metadata such as instrument supplied details of experimental conditions, date, time, reagents etc. may need to be fixed. Others will need updating as the analysis of the data provides amendments or improvements. Keywords and descriptors should also be updatable as the landscape and discipline change.